

Experimental Design for Data science

Intermediate presentation

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Random Sampling Plus Fake Data: Multidimensional Frequency Estimates With Local Differential Privacy

Problem: We want to secure multidimensional data and keep the same frequency of attribute values as the raw data have (with use of differential privacy as well). The current state-of-the-art solution (Smp) may be unfair for some users, and the other one has lower utility (Spl).

Proposed solution: hiding one random attribute and generating fake data for all the other attributes.

Results

Fig 2. Similarities between our and their results for real world dataset

Fig 2. Similarities between our and their results for synthetic dataset

Available code in
Python on GitHub

We got the same
results when
reproducing, but
with slightly
different runtime

Extensions

- Generate new synthetic dataset
- New real world dataset
- Significance testing, are there any differences between different e.g. seeds, sets....

Thank you for your attention!